

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Elton Stafa

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe

Partners

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism

University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse
Ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

Faculty of Political Science
and International Studies
University of Warsaw
University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

UNIVERSIDAD
NACIONAL DE
SAN MARTÍN

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

जवाहरलाल नेहरू विश्वविद्यालय
Jawaharlal Nehru University

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University
of Singapore
National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

Western
UNIVERSITY · CANADA
University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Albania is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

NALAS - Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe: Elton Stafa
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malfertheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Desi Maxwell/Pixabay

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Albania	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Albania: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Decentralized Early Childhood Education</i>	9
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Albania: An Introduction.....	16
3.2. <i>The Allocation of the General-Purpose Unconditional Grant and Fiscal Equalization</i>	19
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Albania: An Introduction	26
4.2. <i>The Territorial and Administrative Reform</i>	29
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania: An Introduction.....	36
5.2. <i>Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination: CLFCC</i>	38
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Albania: An Introduction	44
6.2. <i>Atelier Kanina - 100 Albanian Villages: Civic Engagement Towards Urban-Rural Linkages</i>	48

1. The System of Local Government in Albania

Elton Stafa, NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe

Types of Local Governments

With the 2014 Territorial and Administrative Reform (TAR)¹, in Albania there are two types of local self-governments, i.e. the basic level of local self-government consisting in 61 municipalities (*Bashkia*), and the second tier of local self-government made up of 12 regions (*Qarku*).

Municipalities comprise also administrative units, which can be towns and/or villages. In most cases, the administrative units are the former rural communes that were amalgamated with the TAR with their closest and cultural and historical urban centers. The Municipality of Tirana, for example, is subdivided in 24 administrative units, i.e. 11 subdivisions of the former (urban) municipality and 13 (rural) communes that were amalgamated to Tirana with the TAR. The administration of these units is part of the municipal administration and is directed by an administrator who is appointed and dismissed by the mayor. Towns may be divided into smaller units called quarters (*lagje*). As a rule, a quarter can be established in territories with over 20,000 residents. A town's division into quarters and its territory shall be approved upon a decision of the municipal council.

The regions, the second-tier local self-governments in Albania, were and continue to be entrusted with only few general responsibilities for 'coordination and harmonization' of regional policies with national policies and they may also perform any function that is mandated to them by one or more municipalities within the region or the central government. In practice, the regions do not perform any significant responsibility, other than some administrative tasks delegated by the national government.

Legal Status of Local Governments

The right of local governments to self-government is enshrined in Article 13 of the Constitution of Albania and the Law on Local Self-Government. The constitution prescribes that local government in Albania is based on the principle of decentralization of powers and is exercised according to the principle of local autonomy. The constitutional standing of the second-tier of local self-government, the regional council (*Këshilli i Qarkut*), is the same as for municipalities,

¹ Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania.

regardless of the fact that they have only a few 'coordination' own responsibilities. Only the municipal council (*Këshilli Bashkiak*) is directly elected. The regional council is composed of members from the elected bodies of the municipalities that make up the region, i.e. mayors and other members that are elected from among municipal councilors of the municipalities that compose the region.

The Law on Local Self-Government prescribes the right and the ability of local governments in Albania to regulate and manage public affairs under their own responsibility, within the limits of the law. The exercise of the right of self-government is guaranteed by additional rights of local governments as juridical persons, the right to own and dispose of property, to raise revenues and make expenditures, to perform economic activity, to cooperate with other local governments, etc. The Law on Local Self-Government prescribes also the basic principles of local government finances, according to which, local governments 'shall be entitled, within national financial policies, to adequate financial resources, commensurate with the responsibilities provided for by the Law' (Article 34).²

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

All municipalities are entrusted with general competences to carry out all responsibilities relevant to the local community (as prescribed by law), and any other responsibility that is not specifically assigned (by law) to another level of government. Local governments are entrusted with own and delegated functions and responsibilities. Local self-governments have own responsibilities in the core public services and public infrastructure, in the field of education, social protection, culture, recreation and sports, environmental protection, agriculture, rural development, forests and pastures and protection of nature and biodiversity, local economic development and public order and safety including fire protection. Although these are all 'own' local matters, the degree of political and administrative and fiscal powers decentralized to local governments varies significantly from function to function and in any case, in performing these functions, local governments should also respect regional and national policies and standards for service delivery.

The spirit of the new Law on Local Self-Government entails symmetric decentralization of exclusive functions to all new 61 municipalities, regardless of size, capacity or any other condition that may affect service delivery for particular functions. However, the law introduces also the possibility of asymmetrical decentralization to specific municipalities. However, the transfer of specific responsibilities to specific local governments shall be regulated through a separate law.³ In practice there are a number of cases of asymmetries through transfers of competences to specific local governments for specific purposes, either through a specific law, government decree or a more simple Memorandum of Cooperation between different central

² Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government, Art 34.

³ Law no 139/2015, dated 17 December 2015, on Local Self-Government, Official Gazette No 249, p16963, Art 21.

and local governments. Examples include the transfer of responsibilities for operating and maintaining pre-university students' dormitories, the operation of certain social service centers that were previously operated by a specific line ministry and public order, as the municipal police in Tirana may impose fines for the irregular parking within the territory of the municipality, which is a national police competence.

Political and Social Context in Albania

Albania has a relatively young history of democratic local self-government. While an independent country since 1912, for about half a century (1944-1990), Albania suffered a severe totalitarian regime, during which local government meant simply 'local structures of the (central) government'. Albania began the journey of political and administrative decentralization in 1992 with the first local democratic elections. As in many other ex-communist countries, the early reform processes simply focused on laying down the basic concepts and legal framework for decentralization and local self-government to counter a half century legacy of repressive and non-democratic institutions.⁴ In the early 2000s Albania adopted decentralization reforms that saw the consolidation of local responsibilities and the introduction of basic instruments for the financing of local responsibilities. The reforms enacted between 2014 and 2017, have been even more impactful. In 2014, the Government of Albania (GoA) consolidated 373 urban and rural local governments into 61 municipalities. In 2015, Parliament passed a new Law on Local Self-Government (LSGL)⁵ and a new Law on Local Self-Government Finance (LGFL).⁶ These laws were considered as critical components of a larger strategic plan to expand the role of democratically-elected local governments in Albania by creating larger municipalities and giving them more responsibilities and resources.⁷

Following the collapse of the communist regime, the political landscape is dominated by two major parties, the Democratic Party (DP) and the Social Party (SP). The third largest political party is the Socialist Movement for Integration (SMI). The 2013 general elections were won by a coalition between the SP and the SMI that governed together until the general elections of 2017, since when the SP is governing alone. Local politics is controlled by these three major parties. There have been only a few cases of an independent candidate running a local government as a mayor. The latest case when independent mayors run and took office is the local elections of 2007. Between 2007 and 2011 there have been 12 independent mayors out of 373. After 2011, there have been no cases of independent mayors taking office in Albania.

⁴ Stafa Elton and Xhumari Merita, 'Albania: Aligning Territorial and Fiscal Decentralisation' in William Bartlett, Sanja Kmezić and Katarina Đulić (eds), *Fiscal Decentralisation, Local Government and Policy Reversals in Southeastern Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan 2018).

⁵ Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government (LSGL).

⁶ Law no 68/2017 on Local Self-Government Finance (LSGFL).

⁷ Government of Albania, 'National Crosscutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Government' (adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers no 691 of 29 July 2015).

Regarding the social context of local government, it is important to note the massive number of Albanians that have left the country (but that still have Albanian citizenship) since the early 1990s. Only between 2014 and 2018, about 200,000 Albanians have emigrated while about 100,000 have immigrated.⁸ As for internal population movements, the 2011 census ascertained that the population living in urban areas for the first time exceeded the population living in rural areas. The resident population in urban areas was 53.5 per cent, while 46.5 per cent lived in rural areas.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania

Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

Government of Albania, 'National Crosscutting Strategy for Decentralization and Local Government' (adopted by Decision of the Council of Ministers no 691 of 29 July 2015)

Law no 68/2017 on Local Self-Government Finance

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Stafa E and Xhumari M, 'Albania: Aligning Territorial and Fiscal Decentralisation' in William Bartlett, Sanja Kmezić and Katarina Đulić (eds), *Fiscal Decentralisation, Local Government and Policy Reversals in Southeastern Europe* (Palgrave Macmillan 2018)

⁸ Instat, 'Migration and Migrant Integration' (Instat Institute of Statistics)
<<http://www.instat.gov.al/al/temat/treguesit-demografik%C3%AB-dhe-social%C3%AB/migracioni-dhe-integrimi-i-migrant%C3%ABve/#tab2>>.

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

